

MAINSTREAM BIO

MAINSTREAMING SMALL-SCALE BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS ACROSS RURAL EUROPE

T3.4

Organization of networking and demo days to showcase the deployment of solutions – guidelines

FBCD

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1. Introduction

In line with the other important activities of MainstreamBIO, facilitating the overall aim of the project, the networking events and demo day in task 3.4. contributes to reaching this goal. As stated in the GA, the second expected outcome “Provision of tailored and independent support to innovators to accelerate the development of marketable products and services and improve the market penetration of bio-based solutions in Europe.” Networking plays a very important role in ensuring that innovators can access tailored support across the entire life cycle of bio-based projects, to guide and accelerate the commercialization of their solutions, products and services to offer innovators market insights that can help achieve increased marketability for their products/services and to get small-scale bio-based solutions into mainstream practice across rural Europe, providing a broader range of rural actors with the opportunity to engage in and speed up the development of the bioeconomy all while networking and mentoring help build the skills and collaborations needed to deploy their business models and develop demand-driven bio-based value chains.

According to the Grant Agreement, 2x7 networking events (1 per round, by M24 and M36 respectively) and 1x7 demo day (by M36 combined with networking events) will be organised in Task 3.4 by each of our MIPs in the Netherlands (WR), Poland (IUNG), Denmark (FBCD), Sweden (PROC), Bulgaria (AUP), Spain (INNV) and Ireland (MTU) to **showcase the deployment of solutions** and to **catalyze connections between the supported multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners** (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors) as well as to inspire further actors to get engaged in and support the bioeconomy. To ensure efficiency, the consortium will seek to partner with agricultural or other business events organised in our focal regions.

1.1 Partner’s responsibilities

Task 3.4 is led by FBCD, supported by all partners, and runs from M22 (June 2024) until M36. As the leader of Task 3.4, FBCD is responsible for developing guidelines that facilitate the implementation and conduction of the network events and demo days by the partners who are actively running the Multi-actor Innovation Platforms (MIPs). These guidelines will serve as a framework for effective organisation of the regional network events, ensuring that collective knowledge and expertise are fully utilized.

After the completion of each network events in M24 and M36, the organising partners are required to fill in a reporting template and share it with FBCD.

The implementation of the workshops will be coordinated by:

- **Bulgaria** - conducted and coordinated by **AUP**
- **Denmark** - conducted and coordinated by **FBCD**
- **Ireland** - conducted and coordinated by **MTU**
- **Netherlands** - conducted and coordinated by **WR**
- **Poland** - conducted and coordinated by **IUNG**
- **Spain** - conducted and coordinated by **INNV**
- **Sweden** - conducted and coordinated by **PROC**

The key outcomes of the first network events in M24 will be outlined in a short report on the activities and achievements and will be integrated in D3.1 (M24). As task 3.4 is a part of work package WP3 – Delivery of innovation support accelerating the scale up of small-scale bio-based solutions led by INNV and fulfills the objective 3.4.: Successfully organise a series of networking and demonstration

events to catalyze connections, the outcome of the network events in both M24 and M36 as well as the demo day, will be integrated in D3.3 (M36).

2. Initial guidelines for setting up the network events

This document is intended to support partners in organizing their workshops and missions and will assist in the following paragraphs

- Preliminary analysis of the scope and objectives of the network event.
- Format of the event and demo day.
- Duration and reporting.
- The definition of the participants and the invitation process.

2.1 Objectives of the T3.4 network events and expected outcome

The main goal and objectives of the network events and demo day is to **facilitate connections** between our supported multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors), to inspire further actors to get engaged in and support the bioeconomy as well as to **showcase the deployment of solutions**.

2.2 Time planning of the workshops

The **first round** of network events is planned to take place close to M24, i.e. **M22-M24 (June-August 2024)** of the project.

The **second round** of network events and demo days is planned to take place close to M36, i.e. **M34-M36 (June-August 2025)** of the project.

Demo days can also be included in the first round if it is suitable for the network event.

As stated in the GA, the consortium will seek to partner with agricultural or other business events organised in our focal regions to optimize the organization and recruitment of participants to facilitate connections between our supported multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors).

Overall, all events must have been completed by the end of August 2024 and 2025, respectively. All partners need to provide details about organization like estimated number of participants, venue, type of event, and optionally topics/solutions no later than 2 weeks before the organization of the events.

Table 1. Indicative action plan and individual check list

Action	Who	When	Conducted
Share the 1 st draft of guidelines for MIP leaders	FBCD	June 2024	
Share the final guidelines for MIP leaders	FBCD	Early July 2024	
Event organization & implementation phase	MIP leaders	June – August 2024 (latest end of August)	
Set the date and venue/format and start inviting	MIP leaders	2-4 weeks prior to the event	
Share event plan including final agenda for FBCD and WHITE for dissemination	MIP leaders	2 weeks before the event	
Compile list of participants and distribute final agenda for participants.	MIP leaders	1 week before the event	
Distribute list of participants	MIP leaders	On the date of the event	
Fill out reporting templates and send to FBCD	MIP leaders	After the implementation of the event. All reporting templates should be submitted no later than end of august 2024 (round 1).	
Short report for D3.1	FBCD	August 2024	

2.3 Format and time frame

The format of the events and the final agenda, defined by each workshop organizer, will largely determine the duration of the events. Each partner will determine the duration of the event and the demo day. Given that the event is set to facilitate connections between our supported multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors) as well as to inspire further actors to get engaged in and support the bioeconomy **as well as to** showcase the deployment of solutions, it is recommended to organize the event for at least 1-2 hours.

2.4 Workshops' participants

Open issues and key questions to be considered:

- ✓ Venue and logistics?
- ✓ Topics and themes of the local event/solutions to be show cased?
- ✓ Number of participants?
- ✓ Types of participants? Who are we going to invite?
- ✓ Invitation process (i.e. when, how, preparatory actions etc.)

2.5 Budget and number of participants and invitation process

There is no specific recommended number of participants according to the Grant Agreement. However, given that the main goal of the event is to facilitate connections between our supported

multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors) as well as to inspire further actors to get engaged in and support the bioeconomy as well as to showcase the deployment of solutions, and taken the budget in consideration, it is recommended to organize the event for 20-25 participants per event. There is an allocated budget to each partner for the two (2) networking event and demo day (DoA, pg. 24). The available budget for the implementation of the event and mission is depending on how each partner will organise the event. Ideally, the budget is suggested to cover venue, catering for 20-25 participants per event: **2,000€ per MIP for both network events**. As each MIP leader needs sufficient time to recruit and promote the event for potential participants in MIP leader's network as well as their organisations network and send out invitations.

2.5.1 Types of participants

The participant for the networking event should bring together a diverse group of participants with interest in gaining knowledge about small-scale bio-based projects, that can foster connections between supported multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors) and promote the projects' main goal of setting bio-solutions into mainstream practice across rural Europe and hereby support the development of bioeconomy of Europe. Participants can be comprised of multi-actor partnerships and stakeholders from the target regions involved in the project and representatives of linked networks and initiatives in the regions representing a spectrum of expertise, including primary producers, agricultural students, researchers, entrepreneurs, policymakers, industry representatives, and community leaders.

2.6 Supporting material

A package of supporting material is available before each event for the organizers. This package includes:

- An agenda template which can be adjusted by each MIP Leader according to each workshop's schedule.
- The reporting template, which all MIP Leaders should complete once the event is completed and send to FBCD.
- Presentations of the project – main findings and success stories from the respective MIP partners organizing the events, adjust accordingly for each MIP if needed.

Table 1 presents an overview of the materials needed for each workshop format, along with corresponding file titles and links to access the files on the G-drive.

Table 2. List of CCWs material

Material	File
Organisational guidelines	This document
Agenda template	End of this guideline
Introduction presentation	MainstreamBIO Project overview ReviewMeeting.pptx
Reporting template	End of this guideline
MainstreamBIO leaflets and posters	Visuals & Templates

3. Organizational aspects

Open issues and key questions to be considered:

- ✓ Venue for network event and demo day (M36)
- ✓ Agenda and topics/which cases to showcase?
- ✓ Talks and presentations during the networking event?
- ✓ What is the available budget for the event and how could it be allocated?
- ✓ What will be the format of the event – are there any other agricultural or business events organised in our focal regions to partner up with?

3.1 Location and venue

As facilitation of connections is the main goal in T4.3 the network events are organized as physical meetings. It is recommended to choose a central location in the selected region that is easily accessible for as many participants as possible. To increase the number of participants, it is recommended to organize the event on a location showcasing interesting solutions or persons to give interesting keynote speaks.

It is up to MIP leaders to decide how each event is organized, but one suggestion could be to arrange an event consisting of two parts: a networking event with presentations of selected cases, lunch and a field trip on the premise or close to the venue. Remember to allocate travel time in the agenda if the networking event and the demo site are located at different addresses.

3.2 Facilitator and moderator

- Handling various organisational issues (booking of venue, catering, possible keynote speaker, workshop, show case of demo site) before and on the day of the event.
- Coordinate presentations according to the agenda.
- Monitor time allocation and agenda.
- Follow up after the event.

3.3 Language

Local language or English, depending on preferred language of participants. Reporting template is submitted for FBCD in English.

3.4 Note taking

Notes and photos must be collected to support reporting of the outcomes of the event as well as for communication and dissemination purposes. The notes from the 2 networking events and the demo day will contribute greatly to the outline of a short report, that will contribute to the finalization of the deliverables D3.1, M24 and D3.3, M36.

3.5 Format of the event

It is free for MIPs to decide upon the format of the event. However, networking and physical attendance is crucial.

Overall, each event (and demo day) must:

- ✓ briefly present the main concept of MainstreamBIO and key-achievements
- ✓ facilitate **connections** between our supported multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors)
- ✓ inspire further actors to get engaged in and support the bioeconomy
- ✓ showcase deployment of solutions
- ✓ invite participants to engage in future activities facilitated by MainstreamBIO

General considerations include:

- Depending on number of participants, a roundtable is suitable. In case of many participant (more than 15) an introduction can be served via participant list.
- To facilitate a good dialogue and promote networking, it is recommended to allocate participants into small discussion groups. One way is to form groups in advance in relation to areas of interests such as use of biomasses, business development, nutrient recycling, technologies etc.). Another way is to organize the workshop as a rotation session, with pre-defined, open questions such as 'how you gain access to biomasses, what are your challenges, what are you searching for in the future' etc.

4. GDPR – Informed Consent Form

Important! During the workshops' implementation, personal data (e.g. contact details, group photos or call screenshots) will be collected. It is essential that all project activities fully comply with the Ethics Requirements of the MainstreamBIO project (e.g. compliance with GDPR, obtaining informed consent). To this aim, an informed consent form should be distributed among participants before the event officially begins.

Since the workshops will take place physically, such a form should be signed by each participant (a translated hard copy of the document should be signed).

After your workshop, participants have agreed to the terms and conditions in our consent form, it will be useful if you could take some pictures (or screenshots in case of virtual meeting) of your white boards, post its or of your participants' brainstorming phase.

Important! During network event implementation, personal data (e.g., contact details, group photos) will be collected. It is essential that all project activities fully comply with the Ethics Requirements of the MainstreamBIO project (e.g., compliance with GDPR, obtaining informed consent). To this aim, an informed consent form (see Annex I) should be distributed among participants before the event officially begins.

To ensure collected data can be used, such a form should be signed by participants before the start of the workshop (e.g., digital signature). Since the event will take place physically, a hard-copy of the informed consent form can be distributed and signed *in situ* before the workshop begins. **MIP members do not need to sign informed consent form** since the MIP membership form included participation in activities.

After your event, participants have agreed to the terms and conditions in the consent form, pictures of the group during the activity can be taken. Please, share with WHITE the pictures of the event for D&C purposes.

5. Reporting template

No later than the end of August 2024 (round 1) the organizing partners will have to send to FBCD the reporting template making first sure that it reflects on the following aspects:

1. **General information** (date, place, final agenda, etc.)
2. **Detailed remarks & key-outcomes** from the event's sessions
3. **Communication and dissemination** (e.g. promotional material distributed, stakeholders engaged)
4. **Material and multimedia** provided during the event.

It is important MIP leaders carefully read the reporting template (sent along with this document) to see what they will need to note down during the workshop and what they will have to report to FBCD before they organize and implement the event.

5.1 Template for reporting and suggestion for agenda

Organizational information

MainstreamBIO Partner:

MainstreamBIO Representatives:

Conversion leaders:

- Note-taker:

Date:

Venue:

Agenda:

Activity information

Number of participants: X, of which

- Farmers:
- Producers:
- Regional actors:
- Industry experts:
- Academics:
- Technology enthusiasts:
- Entrepreneurs

General impressions and remarks:

- On the meeting overall: e.g., *Were participants active? If not, how can we encourage participation? Can the methodology be improved?*

Notes: _____

- What did the participants think of the digital toolkit: *e.g., Can the methodology be improved? Is the toolkit user friendly? Which functionalities have raised more interest? Which less interest? Does it include all the useful resources participants would want? What could be better?*

Notes: _____

- Other comments:

Notes: _____

- **Material produced:** *Include the proofs of organisation of the events (pictures)*

Insert picture(s) here

5.2 Template for list of participants

List of participants: *can be printed to be fill-in at the workshop, scanned and added to the feedback report.*

#	Name	Surname	Organisation	Type of stakeholder	Signature
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					
11					
12					
13					
14					
15					
16					
17					
18					
19					
20					
21					
24					
25					

5.3 Informed Consent Form

Each MIP Leader is responsible for translating this form into the local language of the workshop.

Consent Form for the participant in the networking events and demo days.

(To be emailed to participants, and signed and returned prior to the workshop)

Consent questions checklist:	YES	NO
Would you like to take part in the networking event?		
Do you agree to the storage of your contact information from this event until the study end? (August 2025)		
Do you agree to appear in audio/visual material obtained during event?		
Do you agree to dissemination of audio/visual obtained during the event?		
Do you agree to the storage of the audio/visual obtained during the event until the study end? (August 2025)		
Do you agree to your data (name, affiliation, area of expertise) being used in aggregate form in a final report?		

If you want to withdraw your participation in this study, at any stage until August 2025, including any information or audio recordings associated with your participation, you may do so by contacting **XXX(name), XXX@XXX.**

Name: _____

Date: _____

6. Annexes

6.1 Annex I – Participants profile, invitation criteria, supporting materials and promotion recommendations

We encourage the participation of all regional actors including our supported multi-actor partnerships and suitable partners (customers, consumers, tech providers or investors). At this juncture, an initial list of potential participants has been compiled and is suggested to the organizers as suitable for these workshops:

1. Farmers

- Those actively engaged in bioeconomy practices.
- Farmers with varying scales of operations (small, medium, large).

2. Producers

- Individuals or organizations involved in the production of bio-based materials or products.
- Companies incorporating bioeconomy principles into their manufacturing processes.

3. Regional Actors

- Local government representatives and policymakers.
- Environmental organizations and advocates.
- Research institutions focused on bioeconomy.

4. Industry Experts

- Professionals with expertise in bioeconomy and related technologies.
- Scientists and researchers in the field.

5. Academics

- Teachers, professors, or students specializing in bioeconomy or related disciplines.

6. Community Representatives

- Members of local communities affected by or interested in bioeconomy initiatives.
- Non-profit organizations working at the grassroots level.

7. Technology Enthusiasts

- Individuals interested in adopting and promoting sustainable technologies.
- Tech-savvy users who can provide insights into the usability of digital tools.

8. Entrepreneurs

- Individuals exploring business opportunities in the bioeconomy sector.
- Start-up founders with a focus on sustainable practices.

Event promotion/Invitation process - SUGGESTIONS

Creating a successful event promotion and invitation process to attract the target number of participants for the MainstreamBIO networking events is critical. This requires the event to be promoted for a prolonged period (as long as is possible) and increasing the reach and effort of the promotion approaching the date of the event.

1. Develop Compelling Messaging

Crafting a clear and engaging communication strategy, requires the organizer to have in mind the primary objective of this event, which is to facilitate connections and showcase deployment of solutions.

2. Invite the Target Audience

Ask specific individuals within the previously mentioned participant profiles. Tailor your messages (emails) to resonate with each audience segment, addressing their unique interests and concerns. People in your network whom you think would have an interest in joining this event.

The invitation ought to include a request for a response, either by email or registration form linked within the email. Sending invitations to a larger number of people than the desired participants is advisable, considering that not all may be available. Those whose participation is crucial may also be reached through phone calls or informal meetings, it's up to the partner.

In addition to the primary invitations, it's advisable to create a reserve list of participants. This list would serve as a backup in case the initially invited individuals do not confirm their attendance promptly.

Establishing an enrolment deadline allows ample time for sending additional invitations in case of limited participation. Final confirmation can be conducted via phone calls. A week before the workshops, contacting participants to confirm details such as venue, start time, and arrival process is recommended.

3. Utilize Various Communication Channels

After identifying and inviting the target audience, you should disseminate information across various platforms for widespread outreach.

- **Social Media:** Leverage platforms like LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram and, X to share engaging content, event details, and registration links. Use relevant hashtags and tag influencers or organizations in the field.
- **Website and Landing Pages:** Create a dedicated page on your project website with comprehensive information about the workshops, speakers, and registration details.
- **Newsletters:** Include workshop details in regular newsletters, reaching out to existing stakeholders and subscribers.

4. Follow-Up Communication:

Send reminders as the event date approaches. Provide logistical details, access links, and any pre-event materials. Consider sending a post-event survey to gather feedback for future improvements.

5. Monitor and Evaluate:

Track the success of your promotion efforts through metrics like registration numbers, social media engagement, and attendee demographics. Use this data to assess the effectiveness of your promotional strategies.

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The project

MainstreamBIO is a Horizon Europe EU funded project, which sets out to get small-scale bio-based solutions into mainstream practice across rural Europe, providing a broader range of rural actors with the opportunity to engage in and speed up the development of the bioeconomy. Recognizing the paramount importance of bioeconomy for addressing key global environmental and societal challenges, MainstreamBIO develops regional Multi-actor Innovation Platforms in 7 EU countries (PL, DK, SE, BG, ES, IE & NL). The project aims to enhance cooperation among key rural players towards co-creating sustainable business model pathways in line with regional potentials and policy initiatives. MainstreamBIO supports 35 multiactor partnerships to overcome barriers and get bio-based innovations to market with hands-on innovation support, accelerating the development of over 70 marketable bio-based products and services. Furthermore, the project develops and employs a digital toolkit to better match bio-based technologies, social innovations and good nutrient recycling practices with available biomass and market trends as well as to enhance understanding of the bioeconomy with a suite of educational resources building on existing research results and tools. To achieve these targets, MainstreamBIO involves 10 partners across Europe, coming from various fields. Thus, all partners combine their knowledge and experience to promote the growth of bioeconomy in a sustainable and inclusive manner.

Coordinator: **Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Q-PLAN)**

Partner		Short Name
	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN
	MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	MTU
	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR
	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	IUNG
	RISE PROCESSUM AB	PROC
	AGRAREN UNIVERSITET - PLOVDIV	AUP
	FBCD AS	FBCD
	EURIZON SL	INN
	DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL SA	DRAXIS
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